

KLAMA: the Voice from Oral Tradition in Death Rituals to a Work for Choir & Live Electronics

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Abstract — *Klama*, for mixed choir, live electronics & prerecorded sounds, has its origins in the ritual lament of Southern Peloponnese (Greece); a “polyphony” composed of improvised monodies (*moirólóya*), epodes, crying, screams and monologues, accompanied by ritual gestures. By its acoustic violence the lament can be considered an alteration of vocality which affects simultaneously tonality, timbre and language. *Klama* has been developed in three levels, a nexus where vocal writing interacts with electroacoustics and live electronics, the latter seen as a metaphore of the inherent vocal alterations on the lament. In this paper we will show : 1) how the compositional material derived from the voice in oral and byzantine church tradition is explored for the choir and electronic writing; 2) how the three levels of *Klama*, acoustic, electroacoustic & live electronics interact through the act of composition and by means of the technological tools (Open Music, Max/Msp, Audio Sculpt).

Keywords : *lament, vocal techniques, noise, Max/Msp, OpenMusic.*

INTRODUCTION

Klama has been commissioned by Ircam and the Accentus Choir and performed at Agora Festival 2006 at the Centre Pompidou, Paris. It is a work for mixed choir, live electronics and pre-recorded sounds, having its roots in the death rituals, performed in the region of Mani, in Southern Peloponnese. The meaning of the word “*klama*” is simultaneously “cry” and “ritual lament”. It characterizes a “polyphony” encompassing improvised monodies (*moirólóya*), epodes, crying, screams and monologues, accompanied by ritual gestures. Due to its acoustic violence, and related to the experience of loss, lament can be considered more like an alteration of vocality rather than a song; an alteration which, because of the emotional shock, affects tonality, timbre and language as well. Performed by women, mainly in the dead person's house in front of the corpse, this “polyphony” is a kind of accompaniment and appropriation of the dead, reorganizing the social structures. This ritual is followed by the Byzantine monody of an Orthodox Funeral Mass celebrated in church. The two forms are then joined in a complementary and at the same time antithetic way, in a kind of chaotic acoustic dissemination and dispersal.

In the structure of *Klama* my intention was to (keep and) explore this dramatic opposition which separates and brings together two cultures dissimilar to each other, an oral and a textual one. The material of *Klama* originated from the recording of Katerina Xirou's voice, together with others, found and performed in situ.

The musical text evolves in three parallel levels that are superimposed and interact with each other as in Arnulf Rainer's *Übermalungen of Totenmasken* (overpaintings on

the photographed people's death masks). The vocal text uses melodic traits and certain techniques of the mourning voice. The electroacoustic text assembles rough or transformed material, integrating the noise and the deterioration of the analog storage medium (vinyl record and audio tape); mainly focused on timbre, the electronic treatment focalizes on distortion, mask “filtering”, vocal noise simulation, accentuation of breath, amplitude modulation and granular synthesis. It has an effect on the voices of the choir in real time and acts as a metaphor of the vocal perturbations inherent in the lament.

Klama has been composed for an 8-part mixed chamber choir of 33 voices (SSAATTBB) with 3 soloists, soprano, contralto and baritone, who at certain moments join the other parts.

Fig. 1. Choir on stage

Klama develops as a triptych form of three semi-autonomous panels, *klama – melos – diaspora*, bordered and bound by electroacoustic parts.

Intro	Klama	Interlude I	Melos	Interlude II	Diaspora	Finale
	<i>lament</i>		<i>monody</i>		<i>dissemination</i>	

Fig. 2. *Klama* - form

I. COMPOSITIONAL MATERIAL & VOCAL WRITING

A. Compositional material

The compositional material of *Klama* comes from three sources of found and created audio “documents”:

1) mourning and speaking voices and ambient noises form an old audio tape recording of a ritual lament in situ;

2) excerpts of a Katerina Xirou's lament cycle recorded at Ircam and pressed in a vinyl record; 3) excerpts from a hymn of the byzantine Funeral Mass of Ioannis of Damascus (7th-8th centuries). Both electroacoustic & live electronics parts are a deliberate combination of HiFi and LoFi sound. The deteriorated audio tape and vinyl record quality, natural or artificial, offers a large sound palette (noises, crackles, hisses and scratches) determining for the "noise" aesthetics of the work. The vocal, the electroacoustic and the live electronics parts are interwoven and interdependent; these three levels tend to maximal fusion as if past and present formed a continuous circuit, a new acoustic reality where different "époques" co-exist.

B. Text

The text use on *Klama* is restrained, mainly based on the acoustic quality of the phonemes; melted in the sound, rarely perceived, the text is used more as a vehicule of phonetic colors and as a "guide" for the form narratives than for its semantic quality. The Mani's linguistic and poetical idiom, whose imitation is condemned to failure, exists only as "traces" on the fragmented prerecorded voices.

Klama starts with a sequence of five vowels (e i ou a i) derived from the first words of a traditional lament. We can mention shortly some other types of used material: isolated phonemes chosen for their acoustic quality in relationship with vocal register, articulation and intensity; fragmented or entire screaming words; the first word "οιμου" (= imi, a greek exclamation of pain) of the byzantine hymn; the poetic text of a traditional lament in a spoken version.

C. Vocal writing

In Mani's ritual lament tradition we find two types of interpretations of a lament : the *mourning way*, in situ, during death rituals and the *singing way* in an "every day" context. My main interest focuses on the womens' *mourning way* and the *beyond-the-singing* vocal "techniques" and timbres; consequently I chose not to use any modal contents of the singing, the tonally stable "every day" version. As for the fragment of the byzantine hymn, attributed to the male voices only, an approximation of the voice position in the church tradition is demanded.

All vocal parts of *Klama* should be sung without any vibrato. The main vocal techniques used are scream, voiced pant, sob, hoarse voice, "breathing in" and "breathing out" noise, speaking voice sotto voce.

The "melodic" vocal writing is based on: single-tone or drone phrases, sometimes including microtonal fluctuations or short glissandi, and continuous ascending glissandi as those observed at the end of phrases/verses of the laments - often, these phrases are to be sung with a continuous raising intensity until exhale air finishes; two citations, short looped melodies in Byzantine Mode 2, of the world "imi" of the byzantine hymn; short melodic skipping phrases, executed with the chest voice in a high intensity, shapes of real *screams* (words or syllables) often time-expanded. Some other extra-singing sound shapes and rhythmic cells of the mourning voice are used: approximatively pitched, like aspirated *sobs* (descending glissando), noisy and unpitched like short voiced *pants*, long *hoarse voice* sounds and short "breathing in and out

noises. Fast spoken sotto voice passages are used for a traditional lament murmured by the tenors in the singers language. The passage of the score (meas. 55) on "Fig. 3," includes some of the above vocal techniques.

Fig. 3. Vocal techniques for sopranos and contraltos;

scream – aspirated sob – voiced pant – "breathing in" noise.

D. Electroacoustics

The introduction, both interludes and the end of *Klama* are entirely electroacoustic; the introduction is spatialised in the hall during the audience entrance until the choir finds its final position on stage. The sound material uses speaking and mourning voices and ambient noises from an old audio tape recording of a ritual lament in situ and a high pitch-shifted sampled lament of K. Xirou, representing the "announcing bird". The electroacoustic part accompanying throughout the vocal part uses similar transformed audio material integrating deteriorated audio tape and vinyl record sounds. *Klama* ends with vinyl record laments phrases spatialized all around the audience.

II. COMPUTING TOOLS

A set of computing tools has been specially developed for *Klama* at Ircam by Benoit Meudic. They have been used in different steps of the construction of the piece: for the composition of one section of the score (using the OpenMusic software), for the creation of the electronic sounds on studio and for the real time sound treatments of the choir (using the Max/Msp software).

A. Open Music

Open Music is a full visual programming language. It is mainly used by composers for non-real-time generation of symbolic materials (such as midi-files) used for writing scores.

We have chosen this language to emulate a granular synthesis module (*munger~*) taken from the software Max/Msp. We have called our module *simul-munger*. It is written in Common Lisp Language and uses the Open Music graphic interface. The interest of using Open Music stands in the possibility of fine tuning the parameters of the module, and in the conviviality of the symbolic music editors that are provided by the environment. Each time we evaluate the module, it outputs a new 8-voice midi-file that we can visualize in a graphic score editor. The module can potentially provide a great number of different

tuned to a harmonic frequency of the voice, and the second one is the adding of noise filtered by the cepstrum of the voice in a specific frequency range and scaled by the amplitude envelope so that high amplitude levels provide more noise. “Fig. 6,” “voixrauque” (hoarse voice) shows the two areas of the sonagram from which we have defined our module. “Fig. 7,” “bruit” (noise) shows the interface controlling the module.

Fig. 6. The “voixrauque” AudioSculpt sonagram.

Fig. 7. “bruit”. The *bruit* Max/Msp module parameters.

6) *psychoirtrist~*

The *psychoirtrist~* module is a *psola* (pitch-synchronous-overlap-analysis) choral harmonizer developed by Norbert Schnell at Ircam. Applying random temporal and pitch modulation parameters it is used to emulate a choir from the voice of one singer. It has been used on the electroacoustic part of the first section of *Klama* to create progressively a 4-voice virtual choir glissando texture between a given interval (major second and major third) from a single repeated tone phrase of five vowels.

Several other classical treatments such as clipping, frequency filtering, granular synthesis, compressors and delays have been used in the piece in complement to the modules we have described.

C. Spatialisation

Several spatialisation techniques have been used for isolating some singers from the choir. We have used a 6-point diffusion system disposed around the audience.

Fig. 8. Basic loudspeakers configuration

ROOTS & ROUTES

Klama reflects the questioning of compositional approaches and music technologies use which is based on two main axes :

1) the relationship and movement *from orality to textuality* and vice versa; how living oral/aural traditions are conveyed through "voice" (and body) and audio/visual “documents”; how orality, reinforced by personal experience, can be integrated in new forms through textual representation (musical score), material innovation and vocal/instrumental/computer techniques evolution; in which way a foreigner to a given tradition interpreter embodies, mixes, transforms and (re)creates orality to a new milieu. How the musical idea and consequently the text can create topoi and liberate regions (entities from fragments) where different “*époques*” co-exist in constant dialog with each other.

2) the movement *from noise to sound* and vice versa: how found noise models and intentionally inserted noise transforms and becomes part of the musical sound in order to produce a whole new living sound organism; how noise may be used to testify the presence of the medium, the passage of time or the distance of the "source"; how sound/noise can be used as music material in all of its aspects and qualities, from natural to artificial and from "hi-fi" to "lo-fi"; finally how noise, as a positive force dynamically related to sound wouldn't turn to the totalitarianism of the maximum level and of the constant fullness of the sound space.

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